

Superposition of Prime Curvatures and the Graviton - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation of coupling constants magnitudes of the new 8T, and in particular the first representation of net curvature in the context of gravity, it is possible to present a way to create a graviton like particle. That is by combining three prime net curvatures to attain spin two particle.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1); (24 + (3)) + 3; (120 + (3)) + 5; (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. We have been analyzing the propagation of the graviton by the spin two trait, which is the combination of three net curvatures, which could be either distinct or identical. Suppose they are distinct, in order to detect a graviton like particle, which is a superposition of prime curvatures, all we need to do is to find a way for the destabilizer to emit instead of just one, three net prime curvatures. Suppose it is impossible, we could try several destabilizers to emit at the same time and to the same point on the manifold.

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} = \left[2N_{gravity} + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (2)$$

Alternatively:

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V1} + N_{V1} = \left[2N_{gravity} + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.1)$$

Such an analysis is than assuming that there are infinite amounts of spin two particles, which are classified according to the composing elements, which are net curvature of certain magnitude isomorphic to prime number or one. Since the graviton is composite of those net curvature, suppose that one of those net curvature got extracted from the combination, the graviton can not exist anymore.

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} \rightarrow [(2N_{gravity}) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2}$$

Such an analysis is than predicting a much greater dependency and rarity of the graviton upon its composite elements. In contrast to the net curvature with spin one, such as the first three interactions, the graviton is a composite which propagate at short range only. The fact it is short range can come with agreement with the scenario presented in this paragraph. That is, that we can align the three distinct curvature only for a short temporal segments. We assumed it is short ranged as three primes alongside the additional invariant three will yield an even number that vanish.

$$[2N_{gravity} + 2] \rightarrow [2N_{gravity}] \quad (2.11)$$

Prediction one: if we superpose three prime net curvatures, of a certain destabilizer, the result would be Graviton of certain magnitude.

Prediction two: The Graviton is a composite particle. The Gravitons are infinite in kind, and depend upon the composite primes.

In contrast to previous papers about the Graviton, which analyzed the non-vanishing term in equation (2.11), in this paper we analyzed the graviton as the vanishing term, which is the superposition of three net curvatures, which alongside the invariant three, becomes the spin two which vanish. The main point to take from this short essay is that the Graviton is a composite particle of three distinct or identical prime curvatures. The second main point is that the Gravitons are infinite in kind. If we present the primordial in the newer representation of probability, then it becomes clear that the actual detection of the Graviton is unlikely, as it is based upon an infinite chain of depended events with probability smaller than one, due to the fact it is an infinite series.

$$P_{A\#} = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) + \mathcal{M} \right) + P(A) \quad (3)$$

$$A \in \mathbb{P};$$

For each higher term than there is a dependence, assuming same for all for simplicity sake. The next element in the series can only arise after a previous probability was satisfied, as it is a series. So the longer we develop, the smaller the probability to detect the boson as it is depended upon longer chain of events, with probability smaller than one. We can represent it in a simpler fashion by ignoring the constants:

$$P_{A\#} = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) \right) \quad (3.1)$$

Let $A \rightarrow \infty$

$$P_{A\#} = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) \right) \rightarrow 0 \quad (3.11)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)